

THE EMIRATES GROUP

Aviation Safety and Drones: A Global Approach Towards Safe Expansion of the Drone Industry

Hashim Ali Mir

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Primary Supervisor: **Dr. Sevda Ahmadian**

Abstract

The rapid increase in drone usage has been accompanied by a rise in drone-related incidents and accidents, raising concerns about aviation safety. This study, applicable to all categories of drones, adopts a qualitative research methodology to explore both the positive and negative impacts of drones on aviation safety. It evaluates current aviation safety strategies and proposes viable strategic options for effectively integrating drones into safety planning frameworks. The research also examines the dual implications of human factors in drone operations and their influence on safety outcomes. Furthermore, it presents a comprehensive set of best practices and policy recommendations, emphasising the need for aviation regulatory authorities to collaborate with both aviation and non-aviation stakeholders, particularly military aviation, to support a safe expansion of the drone industry. This study provides a foundation for future in-depth research across diverse aspects of unmanned aviation.

List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation/Acronym	Full Form
AC	Advisory Circular
ADS-B	Automatic Dependent Surveillance–Broadcast
AFI–RASP	Africa–Indian Ocean Regional Aviation Safety Plan
AGL	Above ground level
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AP–RASP	Asia–Pacific Regional Aviation Safety Plan
ASTM	American Society for Testing and Materials
ATSB	Australian Transport Safety Bureau
ATTOL	Autonomous Taxi, Take-Off and Landing
BVLOS	Beyond Visual Line of Sight
C-UAS	Counter-Unmanned Aircraft System
CAA	Civil Aviation Authority
DAA	Detect-and-Avoid
DGCA	Directorate General of Civil Aviation (India)
EASA	European Union Aviation Safety Agency
EC	European Commission
eMCO-SiPO	Extended Minimum Crew Operations – Single Pilot Operations
EPAS	European Plan for Aviation Safety
EU	European Union
EUR RASP	European Regional Aviation Safety Plan
EUSCG	European UAS Standards Coordination Group
FAA	Federal Aviation Administration
GASP	Global Aviation Safety Plan
GCAA	General Civil Aviation Authority (UAE)
GAO	Government Accountability Office
GCS	Ground Control Station
GDT	Ground Data Terminal
GMM	General Maintenance Manual
HMI	Human–Machine Interface
IATA	International Air Transport Association
ICAO	International Civil Aviation Organization
IPAS	Icelandic Plan for Aviation Safety
ISM	Industrial, scientific, and medical
KASP	Kazakhstan Aviation Safety Plan
KSA	Kingdom of Saudi Arabia
MID–RASP	Middle East Regional Aviation Safety Plan
MLIT	Ministry of Land, Infrastructure, Transport and Tourism (Japan)
MTOM	Maximum takeoff mass

Abbreviation/Acronym	Full Form
NACC RASP	North American, Central American and Caribbean Regional Aviation Safety Plan
NASP	National Aviation Safety Plan
NTSB	National Transportation Safety Board
R&D	Research and Development
RASP	Regional Aviation Safety Plan
RPA	Remotely piloted aircraft
RPAS	Remotely piloted aircraft system(s)
SAMSP	South American Region Safety Plan
SPAS	State Plan for Aviation Safety
sUAS	Small unmanned aircraft system(s)
SWOT	Strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, threats
TOWS	Threats, opportunities, weaknesses, strengths
UA	Unmanned aircraft
UAE	United Arab Emirates
UAS	Unmanned aircraft system(s)
UAV	Unmanned aerial vehicle
UFM	Unmanned Aircraft Flight Manual
UK	United Kingdom
USD	United States dollar
US	United States

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1. Introduction

This study examines the relationship between drones and aviation safety, focusing on the multifaceted impact of drones, the effectiveness of existing aviation safety strategies, and the role of human factors in drone operations. It also identifies best practices and offers policy recommendations to support the safe and sustainable expansion of the drone industry on a global scale.

1.1 Background of Research

The rapid increase in drone usage across various industries in recent years is expected to accelerate further in the future (EASA 2025a). There has been a corresponding surge in incidents involving unauthorised drones, disrupting aviation operations, and raising safety concerns for manned aircraft (IATA 2025). In response, aviation regulatory authorities are prioritising the safe, secure, and efficient integration of drones into the global air transport system (ICAO 2021a). While measures have been implemented to address current and future safety challenges (ICAO 2021b), the absence of a harmonised global regulatory framework has partially constrained the growth of the drone industry (AW Drones 2022, World Food Programme 2022). This fragmented yet exponential expansion also risks overwhelming existing aviation infrastructure (ICAO 2023a). Ongoing research is exploring ways to adapt infrastructure to accommodate drones effectively (IATA 2023). Efforts continue to address these challenges, emphasising the need for a unified global framework and a holistic approach to ensure both aviation safety and an expansion of the drone industry (EUSCG 2025).

1.2 Justification of Research

The significant growth of the drone industry (EASA 2025a), alongside the rising number of drone-related incidents compromising the safety of manned aircraft (IATA 2025), underscores the urgent need for globally harmonised strategies to safely integrate drones into the existing aviation ecosystem while supporting their continued development (EUSCG 2025). This research examines the intersection of drones and aviation safety, focusing on their impact on manned aircraft. It evaluates the effectiveness of current aviation safety strategies in mitigating risks posed by drones and explores their role in enabling the growth of unmanned aviation. The study also addresses human factors in drone operations, proposing ways to manage these factors to minimise safety risks. Furthermore, it outlines best practices and policy recommendations to facilitate the safe growth of the drone industry.

In essence, this research seeks to bridge the gap between policies, regulations, standards, and procedures governing manned (also referred to as conventional or traditional) and unmanned aviation. By addressing critical safety and integration challenges, it provides a foundational framework for future, in-depth studies on various aspects of unmanned aviation.

1.3 Research Aim

This research aims to explore the impact of drones on aviation safety, evaluate the adequacy of existing aviation safety strategies, study the implications of human factors in drone operations and their effects on aviation safety, and suggest measures to ensure a safe expansion of the drone industry.

1.4 Research Questions

In pursuit of the research aim, this study addresses the following questions:

- What is the impact of drones on aviation safety?
- Have drones been appropriately addressed by aviation safety strategies at

global, regional, and national levels?

- What is the significance of human factors in drone operations and how do they affect aviation safety?
- What measures can be taken to foster the growth of the drone industry without jeopardising aviation safety?

1.5 Research Objectives

The objectives of this research are outlined below:

- To study the impact of drones on aviation safety.
- To evaluate the aviation safety strategies for drones.
- To investigate the human factors in drone operations along with their effects on aviation safety.
- To outline best practices and recommend new policies for safe expansion of the drone industry.

1.6 Overview

The second chapter of this research presents a comprehensive literature review, offering an overview of existing studies and relevant concepts to establish the foundation for the research. Chapter 3 explains the methodology and research design. Chapter 4 presents the raw data and factual results without interpretation. Chapter 5 presents the findings, summarising key patterns observed in the results. Chapter 6 provides an in-depth analysis of the results, while Chapter 7 discusses the findings and analysis within the broader context of the research. Chapter 8 concludes the study with a summary of outcomes, and Chapter 9 presents key recommendations and areas for future research.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

This chapter reviews the existing literature on aviation safety and drones. It synthesises key studies, highlights their strengths and weaknesses, evaluates how this research builds on existing knowledge and addresses gaps in the literature, and identifies avenues for future research. The focus areas include the impact of drones on aviation safety, safety strategies for drones, human factors in drone operations and their effects on aviation safety, and best practices and policy recommendations for safe expansion of the drone industry.

2.2 Methodology for the Literature Review

The literature search was conducted thematically, aligning with the four Research Objectives. Google Scholar was chosen as the primary database due to its broad access to scholarly literature, though it includes a mix of peer-reviewed and non-peer-reviewed sources. Priority was given to peer-reviewed sources and highly cited studies, while other credible publications were also considered where necessary.

Boolean operators (AND, OR) were used to refine queries, with keywords including, but not limited to, drones, unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV), unmanned aircraft (UA), unmanned aircraft system (UAS), remotely piloted aircraft (RPA), remotely piloted aircraft system (RPAS), impacts, aviation, aerodrome, airline, safety, strategies, global, regional, national, human factors, drone operations, industry, best practices, and policies. To ensure relevance, searches were generally restricted to 2022–2024 (extended to 2022–2025 from 1 January 2025). On average, the first 100 results were reviewed for each query. Selection was based on title relevance, followed by abstract and conclusion evaluation. A total of 46 publications were excluded after a detailed review due to lack of relevance, insufficient details, or lower credibility.

2.3 Impact of Drones on Aviation Safety

2.3.1 Drones and their Classifications

A drone, also known as UAV, UA, or RPA, is an aircraft that operates without an onboard pilot. It can have varying levels of autonomy, ranging from manual control to full autonomy (Aibin et al. 2021, BALMUŞ 2023, Nowacki and Bolz 2022). A drone serves as the airborne component of a UAS or RPAS, which typically includes ground-based elements such as Ground Control Station (GCS) and Ground Data Terminal (GDT). A GCS is used to operate the drone, while GDT facilitates communication with it (ICAO 2021b, Ramesh and Muruga Lal Jeyan 2022).

Drones are classified based on various parameters, including operational risk (EASA 2025b), maximum takeoff mass (MTOM), flying principle, level of autonomy, mission type (e.g., reconnaissance, surveillance, attack, transport, search and rescue), propulsion system, range (altitude, datalink), application (military, civilian), launch method (ground, air, sea), size, endurance, and payload type (e.g., sensors, cameras, communication systems, weapons, cargo). These classifications can have further subclassifications, and a single drone can combine attributes from multiple categories, making it a hybrid of various classifications (Ahmed et al. 2022, Lyu et al. 2023, Mohsan et al. 2022, Nespolo 2023, Sabour, Jafary, and Nematiyan 2023, Telli et al. 2023).

2.3.2 Negative Impacts of Drones on Aviation Safety

Safety can be defined as the absence of unacceptable risks and being at risk means being

exposed to danger (Allouch et al. 2019, Fox 2020). As one of the latest threats to aviation safety, drones can inflict more damage to manned aircraft than birds in the event of a collision (Gong et al. 2019, Guzanek and Borucka 2021). While drones have not yet caused a fatal accident involving a commercial airliner, several incidents highlight their disruptive potential. In 2018, a helicopter crashed in South Carolina, United States (US), while avoiding a small drone. In 2019, Newark Airport, US, shut down for 30 minutes after airline pilots reported drones at 3,500 feet above ground level (AGL), causing flight diversions. In 2021, a drone collided with a helicopter in Chile, injuring a passenger (McLachlan et al. 2022, Shrestha 2021).

Loss of control due to strong winds and incorrect altitude readings caused by non-standardised altimeters on drones can result in potential collisions with manned aircraft (Singh 2022, Torens et al. 2020). Additionally, immature Detect-and-Avoid (DAA) technology and the absence of transponders or Automatic Dependent Surveillance–Broadcast (ADS-B) systems further limit drones' ability to avoid mid-air collisions (Ribeiro, Ellerbroek, and Hoekstra 2020, Wheeler, Duboc, and St Amand 2020). Compounding these issues, most drones operate on industrial, scientific, and medical (ISM) frequency bands, which makes them difficult to detect using radio frequency techniques near airports (Chiper et al. 2022). Furthermore, as cyber-physical systems, drones are vulnerable to unauthorised access by third parties, potentially leading to loss of operator control (Allouch et al. 2019, Baballe et al. 2022).

2.3.3 Positive Impacts of Drones on Aviation Safety

Drones equipped with sensors and cameras along with Artificial Intelligence (AI)-powered image processing, have the potential to enhance traditional human-led aircraft and runway inspections and reduce the risk of human error (Rodríguez et al. 2024, Suvittawat and Ribeiro 2024). In addition, drones are capable of providing valuable insights into the surface conditions of aprons and taxiways (Kovács et al. 2024). They are also able to improve Foreign Object Debris detection, providing immediate, accurate, and reliable results while minimising runway closures and disruptions, thereby boosting operational efficiency (Ibrahim et al. 2023). Drones may also enhance airport safety by enabling real-time bird detection and assisting in nighttime wildlife monitoring with thermal cameras (Drennan et al. 2023, Said Hamed Alzadjali et al. 2024). These advancements showcase their potentially transformative role in aircraft, airport, and runway inspections, significantly improving aviation safety.

2.4 Aviation Safety Strategies and Drones

Strategy is a long-term plan aimed at achieving specific goals across various domains (Cambridge Dictionary 2025a, Collins Dictionary 2025a, Oxford Learner's Dictionaries 2025a). Global Aviation Safety Plan (GASP) by the International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO) serves as the global aviation safety strategy, focusing on reducing risks and improving safety. ICAO, a United Nations agency with 193 member states, guides the aviation industry's sustainable growth (ICAO 2021c, 2022a). GASP provides the framework for Regional Aviation Safety Plans (RASPs) and National Aviation Safety Plans (NASPs), ensuring alignment from global to national levels (ICAO 2021d, 2021e, 2022a). The European Plan for Aviation Safety (EPAS), published by European Union Aviation Safety Agency (EASA), can be considered the European Union (EU) equivalent of the European RASP (EUR RASP) by ICAO (EASA 2023a, ICAO 2021f, 2022a). EASA, with 31 EU member states, plays a key role in global aviation safety, aligning with international standards and maintaining partnerships

with over 100 countries (EASA 2025c). The European Commission (EC), as the EU's executive body, oversees policy implementation, international negotiations, and coordination among EU member states (EC 2025).

ICAO anticipates that a significant number of drones will operate alongside manned aviation in shared airspace by 2030 (Maly et al. 2023). EASA's Counter-UAS (C-UAS) Action Plan advises aerodromes to integrate safety-security risk assessments, mitigate drone intrusion impacts, and deploy counter-drone systems to enhance aviation safety (Pascarella et al. 2022). The EC's Drone Strategy 2.0 aims to harness the societal and economic benefits of drones while ensuring safe, secure, and sustainable integration into the European airspace (Truxal and Scott 2024). The EC's strategic priorities include developing an EU-wide, ICAO-aligned and harmonised regulatory framework for drones, enhancing operator awareness of rules to prevent mid-air collisions between manned and unmanned aircraft, a key risk area according to EASA's analysis of occurrences (Osiecki, Cyran, and Dębowski 2024, Truxal and Scott 2024).

2.5 Human Factors in Drone Operations and their Effects on Aviation Safety

2.5.1 Types of Drone Operations

Operations refer to the activities or a set of planned actions undertaken to make a system function for a particular purpose (Cambridge Dictionary 2025b, Oxford Learner's Dictionaries 2025b, The Britannica Dictionary 2025a). In contrast, applications refer to the practical ways in which something is used in a particular context or for a specific purpose (Cambridge Dictionary 2025c, Collins Dictionary 2025b, Merriam-Webster 2025a, Oxford Learner's Dictionaries 2025c, The Britannica Dictionary 2025b). Drones serve both commercial and military purposes, with applications in surveillance, logistics, agriculture, transportation, goods delivery, construction, and more (Gugan and Haque 2023, Szóstak et al. 2023).

Pre-flight operations may involve determining the operational risk, applying mitigation measures, reviewing regulations, planning the mission, performing maintenance, conducting inspections, and ensuring UAS readiness. During flight, tasks can include drone control, emergency management, airborne monitoring, data acquisition, and landing. Post-flight activities often include data processing and analysis in addition to the routine inspections (Szóstak et al. 2023, van der Sluijs et al. 2023).

2.5.2 Significance and Dual Impacts of Human Factors in Drone Operations

Human factors consider the characteristics, capabilities, and limitations of humans for their interaction with different systems to perform various tasks (FAA 2022a). Unintentional deviation from safe practice is termed an error from aviation safety's perspective. Latent (or hidden) errors are organisational, whereas active errors are related to individuals (Sameera, Bindra, and Rath 2021).

Unlike the pilots of manned aircraft, drone operators are unable to rely on direct sensory cues for visual and auditory feedback from the aircraft's surroundings. Consequently, the situational awareness of drone operators is reduced as they are isolated from the aircraft; it can be further reduced due to poorly designed displays of the ground-based systems, thereby increasing the likelihood of human errors due to misinterpretation of the alerting information. The reduced situational awareness can adversely impact the operator's efficiency and effectiveness in handling an emergency (Kille et al. 2021).

Despite increased automation in drone operations, human error remains a leading cause of accidents (Mygal 2022). Even in drones equipped with full autonomy, human intervention may

still be required during emergencies (Aibin et al. 2021). However, such transitions towards greater levels of human control are inherently challenging as they drastically increase the operator's workload (Grindley et al. 2024a). Decision errors are more likely to occur in these situations, especially if checklists are unclear or inadequate, reducing the operator's ability to manage in-flight emergencies effectively (Grindley et al. 2024b). In addition, because of the rapid technological advancements in drones, the dynamics of maintenance operations are also changing continuously, which should be taken into consideration from the human factors point of view to avoid skill-based errors (Nicklin 2022).

2.6 Best Practices and Policies for Safe Expansion of the Drone Industry

Best practices are the recognised methods or procedures expected to produce optimal results and are considered suitable for widespread adoption (Collins Dictionary 2025c, Merriam-Webster 2025b). A policy, on the other hand, refers to an officially agreed-upon, high-level overall plan or a set of acceptable procedures chosen from alternatives to serve a particular purpose in a given situation (Cambridge Dictionary 2025d, Merriam-Webster 2025c).

2.6.1 Best Practices

Australia's regulatory landscape recognises drones as an aviation safety risk while supporting their growth. Since 2002, the country has consistently updated its regulations to ensure a safe expansion of the drone industry (Zenz 2023). Canada's stringent regulations have significantly reduced drone-related incidents since 2017. They mandate drone registration and operator training on air laws and safety protocols. Coordination with Air Traffic Control is required for drones exceeding MTOM of 25 kilograms, flying above 400 feet AGL, or conducting Beyond Visual Line of Sight (BVLOS) operations (Wanner et al. 2024). Unlike Visual Line of Sight operations, BVLOS operations allow remote control without direct visual contact (Anicho, Nagar, and Bansal 2024).

In the US, drones weighing over 250 grams must be registered with the Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) and broadcast remote identification, including location and performance data, for BVLOS operations. EASA classifies drone operations into three risk-based categories. The Open category (low risk) restricts drones from flying above 120 metres, the Specific category (medium risk) allows flights above 120 metres with permission, and the Certified category (high risk) requires special permits. All operators are mandated to undergo training, except those flying drones under 250 grams. In Japan, drones over 100 grams must be registered (Lee, Hess, and Heldeweg 2022). Following the 2024 Noto earthquake, which caused over 240 deaths and damaged approximately 60,000 buildings, government agencies of Japan collaborated with private drone companies to integrate drones into disaster management, addressing regulatory gaps through special exemptions for rapid deployment (Ishiwatari 2024, Suppasri et al. 2024).

2.6.2 Policy Recommendations

The rapid expansion of the drone industry without an adequate regulatory framework poses a threat to aviation safety (Park et al. 2021). The availability of proactively developed appropriate policies is essential for safe growth of the drone industry (Fox 2022). The economic potential of this promising market sector can be fully harnessed by liberalising drone laws while ensuring aviation safety (Kapustina et al. 2021).

A harmonised global effort for the legal framework, incorporation of advanced and reliable technologies, continued refinement of the certification processes for drone operators as well as

proactive identification of regulatory gaps through the development and implementation of a system to track drone-related incidents and accidents are expected to encourage a safe expansion of the drone industry (Wanner et al. 2024). The vulnerabilities of drones from the cybersecurity point of view also need to be addressed to ensure the operations are more reliable (Mohsan et al. 2023). Furthermore, the development of highly effective and efficient C-UAS technologies may be undertaken for deployment at airports to avoid a fatal accident due to unauthorised drone intrusion (Park et al. 2021).

Pre-negotiated public-private partnerships between governments and drone operators are also recommended to prevent deployment delays in disasters (Ishiwatari 2024, Kang et al. 2024). Aviation safety strategies for drones should be prioritised based on their importance and feasibility (Yang, Chang, and Lin 2022). Most importantly, strict enforcement of the existing regulations is essential to ensure aviation safety (Alamouri, Lampert, and Gerke 2023).

2.7 Analysis

Existing research proactively focuses on the potential threats drones pose to aviation safety (Gong et al. 2019, Guzanek and Borucka 2021). A recent incident in the US, where a civilian drone collided with a firefighting aircraft of the Los Angeles County Fire Department on 9 January 2025, can be considered another reminder of the disruptive potential of drones. The collision caused severe damage to the aircraft, leading to its grounding and interrupting firefighting efforts at a critical stage (Los Angeles County Fire Department 2025). Although temporary flight restrictions for drones were in place at the time of collision, and FAA regulations impose an imprisonment of up to 12 months for such violations, the incident highlights how ignorance of regulations and irresponsible actions by drone operators can pose a significant threat to aviation safety (US Department of Justice 2025).

While most research focuses on the negative impacts of drones on aviation safety, an alternative perspective, that drones can also be used to enhance aviation safety, is gaining attention. Their role in improving human-led inspections, as well as enhancing safety and operational efficiency, has been highlighted in recent studies (Drennan et al. 2023, Ibrahim et al. 2023, Kovács et al. 2024, Rodríguez et al. 2024, Said Hamed Alzadjali et al. 2024, Suvittawat and Ribeiro 2024).

This perspective is further supported by real-world developments. In 2024, Delta Air Lines received FAA approval to use drones for conducting maintenance inspections following lightning strike events. The airline reports that drone-assisted inspections enable its maintenance team to assess aircraft conditions up to 82% faster (Delta 2025). Emirates and Boeing also signed a Memorandum of Understanding in 2023 to advance drone-assisted aircraft inspections for enhancing maintenance operations (Emirates 2023).

While researchers have addressed EASA's C-UAS Action Plan and EC's Drone Strategy 2.0, a gap remains in evaluation of the existing GASP, RASPs, and NASPs with regards to drones (Osiecki, Cyran, and Dębowski 2024, Pascarella et al. 2022, Truxal and Scott 2024). A significant number of published studies address both the positive and negative impacts of human factors in drone operations from the operator's standpoint, with a focus on active errors (Aibin et al. 2021, Grindley et al. 2024a, Kille et al. 2021). But their corresponding effects on aviation safety remain underexplored.

Some aspects of latent errors have also been briefly highlighted in the existing research, particularly the likelihood of decision errors by drone operators due to unclear or inadequate

checklists (Grindley et al. 2024b, Nicklin 2022). It is essential to highlight that inadequate checklists and aircraft manuals have already resulted in major aviation accidents. One of the contributing factors in the crash of Lion Air Flight 610 on 29 October 2018, involving a Boeing 737-8 MAX, was inadequate information in the flight manual. A malfunction in the newly installed software-based flight control system caused the crash, killing all 189 occupants, as pilots were unable to manage the system failure (Komite Nasional Keselamatan Transportasi Indonesia 2019). Likewise, unclear or inadequate checklists and manuals for drones could lead to active errors by drone operators, potentially compromising aviation safety.

The existing research also indicates that the maintenance personnel are more likely to make skill-based errors if continuously evolving dynamics of maintenance operations in drones are not adequately addressed (Grindley et al. 2024b, Nicklin 2022). It is important to note that maintenance practices of drones differ from those of traditional manned aircraft and are highly dynamic, particularly for drones weighing up to 25 kilograms. As a result, maintenance personnel in the drone industry require a distinct skill set, which should be updated more frequently. Another grey area in drone maintenance is the lack of well-documented and clearly defined guidance and instructions, which increases the likelihood of errors in maintenance procedures compared to the structured documentation used for manned aircraft (Karunakaran 2022). Therefore, human factors in drone maintenance operations require careful planning and execution to mitigate both direct and indirect negative effects on aviation safety.

There is a general agreement among researchers that new and harmonised policies are essential to foster the growth of the drone industry while mitigating threats to aviation safety (Fox 2022, Kapustina et al. 2021, Park et al. 2021, Wanner et al. 2024). Pre-negotiated public-private partnerships between governments and drone operators have also been proposed to facilitate the efficient deployment of drones in disaster scenarios (Ishiwatari 2024, Kang et al. 2024). These arguments are valid because a mismatch between global policies and local regulations can hinder the growth of any industry, while public-private partnerships within a state can contribute to the development of more effective regulations (Lowell et al. 2024). According to the US Food and Drug Administration, global regulatory harmonisation can enhance drug safety and serve as a catalyst for industry development (Ramanadham 2022). Therefore, a globally harmonised regulatory framework for drones appears to be an ideal solution.

However, achieving a fully harmonised global policy may not be practicable given the unique political, cultural, and economic contexts of sovereign nations (Lowell et al. 2024). For instance, China follows a top-down, government-led model, whereas the US adopts a more decentralised, market-driven approach to drone industry policies (Skorup and Gu 2022). Moreover, advanced economies, including the US, the EU, and China, tend to play a more prominent role in shaping industrial policy interventions on a global scale (Ilyina, Pazarbasioglu, and Ruta 2024).

2.8 Conclusion

Drones are primarily a threat to aviation safety, yet they also offer opportunities to enhance it, making it essential to explore their overall impact beyond existing literature. Likewise, human factors influence drone operations both positively and negatively, potentially impacting aviation safety in a similar manner. Therefore, an in-depth investigation into human factors in drone operations and their implications for aviation safety is necessary. While certain drone-related strategies have been addressed in the current literature, existing aviation safety plans

should also be evaluated for their relevance to drones. Global policy harmonisation is also crucial to ensuring the safe expansion of the drone industry. Thus, outlining best practices can help shape effective, evidence-based policies (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development 2024).

This research explores the impacts of drones on aviation safety and evaluates the effectiveness of existing aviation safety strategies concerning drones at global, regional, and national levels. It investigates human factors in drone operations along with their impacts on aviation safety. It also presents a comprehensive set of best practices and policy recommendations aimed at ensuring a safe expansion of the drone industry.

This research aims to address gaps in the existing literature by providing an in-depth analysis of the GASP, RASPs, NASPs, and EPAS concerning drones, identifying their strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats to generate viable strategic options. Additionally, it seeks to examine the positive and negative impacts of human factors in drone operations along with their effects on aviation safety, while also exploring latent errors and proposing possible preventive measures.

Future research avenues may include identifying drone application areas that do not pose a direct threat to aviation safety, allowing the drone industry to grow within safer operational domains. In addition, future research could explore licensing requirements for engineers and technicians involved in drone maintenance. Cybersecurity challenges in drones may also be examined in greater depth to propose necessary mitigation strategies. Furthermore, studies could investigate the challenges associated with the implementation of existing drone regulations.

3. Methodology

3.1 Introduction

This chapter describes the research philosophy, approach, and strategy, followed by an explanation of the data collection methods. It also details the tools and techniques used for data analysis.

3.2 Research Design

3.2.1 Research Philosophy (Interpretivism)

Interpretivism was preferred as the way in which data about aviation safety and drones was collected, analysed, and used to help formulate a global approach towards safe expansion of the drone industry, primarily due to the lack of adequate and consistent safety-related data for drones (Kasprzyk and Konert 2021). Additionally, as drones have already been identified as an emerging issue in multiple aviation safety strategies (Commonwealth of Australia 2024, ICAO 2023b), an investigation of the contextual factors for deeper understanding was necessary. Therefore, focusing on subjective meanings and considering unique human experiences was deemed appropriate for constructing meaningful insights.

3.2.2 Research Approach (Inductive)

An inductive approach was selected because the research aimed to develop a generalised global viewpoint applicable to all categories of drones to support a safe expansion of the unmanned aviation industry. This approach was appropriate as it allowed the research to begin with specific observations and progress towards broader generalisations. Given that the drone industry is rapidly evolving (Nicklin 2022) and lacks an adequate amount of consistent safety-related data (Kasprzyk and Konert 2021), an inductive approach offered greater flexibility for deeper exploration. It enabled the construction of knowledge from the ground up, supporting the development of new insights into the impact of drones on aviation safety and facilitating the identification of patterns prior to proposing evidence-based policy recommendations.

3.2.3 Research Strategy (Qualitative)

The inductive approach was implemented by interviewing three experts from the industry and by collecting data from a wide range of credible sources across the regulatory, industry, academic, government, military, and public service domains. In light of the limited availability of reliable statistical safety data related to drones (Kasprzyk and Konert 2021), a qualitative research strategy was considered well-suited for interpreting meanings, themes, and patterns within the collected data.

3.3 Data Collection

3.3.1 Primary Data Sources (Expert Interviews)

In-depth insights and perspectives relevant to the research were gathered by conducting semi-structured, one-to-one interviews with three experts in the industry, selected based on their extensive experience and subject-matter knowledge. To preserve confidentiality, specific identities and affiliations are not disclosed.

Two of the experts had experience in both manned and unmanned aviation, while the third specialised exclusively in UAS. Collectively, they brought substantial expertise across operations, maintenance, and research and development (R&D). One of the experts was a former naval aviation officer who is currently the head of the UAS training department at an aviation technical college. The expert holds rotary-wing qualifications along with six years of command experience in a UAV squadron. The expert has over 25 years of combined experience

in civil and military aviation.

The second expert was a former Air Force officer who is currently the UAS curriculum development and instructional design specialist at an aviation technical college. The expert holds a master's degree in avionics engineering, has maintenance management experience for various manned aircraft, has flown over 2,000 hours as a flight engineer, and has participated in drone accident investigations. The expert's combined civil and military aviation experience spans over 30 years. The third expert was an electrical engineer with operational and R&D experience in UAS. The expert is currently working as a technical instructor for a UAS maintenance programme at an aviation technical college and has a total of 10 years of experience in the drone industry.

3.3.2 Secondary Data Sources

Secondary data to support the research were collected from a wide range of credible sources across the regulatory, industry, academic, government, military, and public service domains. These included, but were not limited to, the official websites of ICAO, EASA, FAA, National Transportation Safety Board (NTSB), Australian Transport Safety Bureau (ATSB), Airbus, DJI, General Atomics Aeronautical, Australian Army Research Centre, the Ministry of Land, Infrastructure, Transport and Tourism (MLIT) Japan, and the Government of Canada.

For the evaluation of aviation safety strategies, secondary data were collected from the most recent editions of the GASP, RASPs, NASPs, and the EPAS as available on the ICAO's official website. Out of a total of 94 NASPs reviewed, 28 were excluded because they were not available in English. The remaining 66 NASPs were assessed based on the presence of drone-related terms which included but were not limited to drone, UAV, UAS, RPA, and RPAS. Based on the presence of these drone-related terms along with the geographic distribution of the countries as well as their influence in shaping the industrial policy at a global scale (Ilyina, Pazarbasioglu, and Ruta 2024), 10 were selected to ensure that the final set of NASPs provided a reasonably comprehensive global representation. These included Australia, China, Finland, India, Iran, Jamaica, Sierra Leone, the United Arab Emirates (UAE), the United Kingdom (UK), and the US.

3.4 Data Analysis

Thematic analysis was used to present findings in Chapter 5, summarising key patterns observed in the results outlined in Chapter 4. The results were further analysed and discussed in Chapter 6 and Chapter 7, using SWOT (strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, threats) analysis and TOWS (threats, opportunities, weaknesses, strengths) matrix, respectively.

3.4.1 Thematic Analysis (Adapted Braun and Clarke Approach)

Braun and Clarke's six-step thematic analysis approach was used to present the findings in Chapter 5. The approach was adapted to align with the structure and objectives of this research. For instance, Step 5 (Defining and Naming Themes) was not applied in the traditional sense, as the results in Chapter 4 were already organised under four pre-determined research themes. Similarly, a component of Step 1 (Familiarisation with the Data), which involves transcribing and reviewing the interviews, had already been completed during the development of Chapter 4, where the secondary data were extracted from the verbatim transcriptions of expert interviews. A semantic approach was adopted, focusing on the explicit content of the data to identify key points of convergence and divergence between primary and secondary data presented in Chapter 4 (Braun and Clarke 2006).

3.4.2 SWOT Analysis and TOWS Matrix

An in-depth analysis of aviation safety strategies for drones was conducted in Chapter 6 (Analysis) using the SWOT analysis. Strengths and weaknesses were identified from the current edition of the GASP, while opportunities and threats were derived from EPAS, RASPs, and the selected NASPs. The TOWS matrix was then applied in Chapter 7 (Discussion) to develop strategic options based on the identified strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats (Benzaghta et al. 2021, Liangrokapart and Sittiwatethanasiri 2023). Complete details of the SWOT analysis and the TOWS matrix are provided in Appendix A.

4. Results

4.1 Insights from Expert Interviews (Primary Data)

4.1.1 Impact of Drones on Aviation Safety

One of the experts highlighted that pilots of manned aircraft are required to be cautious of potential encounters with drones in addition to birds. Another expert pointed out that a large number of drones can be operated virtually from any location, including rooftops, and often without registration, posing a significant challenge to aviation safety. The experts stated that drone crashes also have the potential to cause injuries, fatalities, or property damage on the ground.

The importance of a flexible yet robust regulatory framework was emphasised to mitigate the negative impacts of drones on aviation safety, with advocacy for cross-sector collaboration, involving both aviation and non-aviation stakeholders. One expert emphasised the need for regulatory frameworks to require licensing for all drone operators, including recreational users, and to mandate the registration of any drone that poses a potential threat to aviation safety, irrespective of its weight. They emphasised a system-wide approach over isolated technologies, identifying public awareness, enforcement mechanisms, comprehensive training for both manned and unmanned aviation personnel, real-time tracking of drones, and reliable DAA capabilities as critical elements. They also argued that DAA systems assist in collision avoidance, but further development is needed to enhance their decision-making capabilities.

In response to questions regarding the positive impacts of drones on aviation safety, experts stated that DAA systems developed for autonomous flight in drones can also be adapted for use in manned aircraft once standardised. One expert pointed out that the concept of a single-pilot cockpit in commercial manned aircraft has been influenced by advancements in drone technology. They also highlighted indirect positive impacts, stating that drones are increasingly replacing manned aircraft in certain high-risk operations, such as power line inspections and search and rescue missions. To maximise the safety benefits offered by drones, the experts emphasised that the technical capabilities of the drone industry should not remain underutilised due to the lack of a clear regulatory framework.

4.1.2 Aviation Safety Strategies and Drones

According to one of the experts, near-term drone applications should not pose a direct threat to aviation safety and may include agriculture, emergency response, traffic regulation, and mapping services. The expert further added that effective management will be necessary for inter-drone operations within these application areas.

Another expert proposed that a feasibility study could be undertaken to assess the viability of operating drones on frequencies outside the ISM bands, or to examine the potential allocation of dedicated frequency bands specifically for drone operations. The expert further emphasised that, regardless of the frequency band employed, drone operations should avoid areas in close proximity to high-power radio transmissions due to the associated risk of signal interference.

4.1.3 Human Factors in Drone Operations and their Effects on Aviation Safety

Experts identified a knowledge gap between professionals in the drone industry and those in manned aviation, viewing it as a potential risk to aviation safety as drones begin operating in the shared airspace. Unlike licensed personnel in manned aviation who receive formal training and possess operational experience, many individuals involved in drone operations, maintenance, and design come from non-aviation backgrounds and lack awareness of safety

protocols and regulations. Based on two incidents from personal experience, one expert pointed out that human error by manned aviation personnel, both military and civilian, can lead to a collision between manned and unmanned aircraft, particularly when airspace designated for drone activity is violated by pilots of manned aircraft.

All experts stated that autonomous systems in drones have become safer and more reliable than manual operations by reducing the likelihood of human error and shifting the operator's role to system monitoring. However, they pointed out that reduced workload may lead to decreased alertness and complacency, increasing the risk of oversight errors. One expert added that human errors in mission planning, communication, and decision-making can still introduce risks in autonomous drone operations. While discussing the positive impacts of human factors in drone operations and their effects on aviation safety, the experts argued that autonomous systems may outperform humans in routine tasks, but human judgment remains superior in complex or unexpected situations.

Comprehensive and standardised training for both manned and unmanned aviation personnel was emphasised to address human factors effectively. In the context of unmanned systems, experts stressed that operator training should focus more on system management rather than manual control skills, with particular attention to air traffic coordination and emergency procedures. Public awareness campaigns, regular refresher trainings, and structured systems for reporting and investigation of incidents and accidents were also considered essential components of a strong safety framework.

While discussing latent errors in drone operations, one of the experts pointed out that Human–Machine Interface (HMI) in drones lacks standardisation, making transitions between UAV systems difficult and necessitating additional training. Moreover, the lack of standardised manuals and documentation was identified by all experts as a major concern, attributed to manufacturers' limited aviation background. To address these issues, they recommended standardising HMI designs, implementing well-defined regulations, enforcing safety and quality standards, and mandating comprehensive and regularly updated manuals through appropriate regulatory frameworks. As a preventive measure, one of the experts advised conducting practical trials of procured UAS prior to deployment to identify any gaps in the documentation.

4.1.4 Best Practices and Policies for Safe Expansion of the Drone Industry

One of the experts shared that their team developed operational procedures for military drones with MTOM of 50–100 kilograms in close collaboration with the regulatory authority. By drawing on the authority's expertise and leveraging regulatory openness, they were able to operate near an international airport without disrupting civil air traffic. The expert further emphasised that a best practice from manned aviation, updating procedures following incidents and accidents, can be adopted by the drone industry to enhance operational safety.

The policy measures recommended by the experts for a safe expansion of the drone industry included enhanced collaboration between the industry and regulatory authorities; safety-focused operator training tailored to drone categories; standardisation of critical UAS components to improve reliability; the adoption of drone tracking mechanisms without overly restrictive regulations, ensuring both safety and cost-effectiveness; and the promotion of drones in low-risk sectors such as agriculture and infrastructure monitoring. In addition, two experts recommended establishing dedicated licensing frameworks for drone engineers and

technicians, distinct from the traditional licensing categories used for conventional aviation maintenance personnel.

4.2 Summary of Secondary Data

4.2.1 Impact of Drones on Aviation Safety

According to EASA, pilots of the manned aircraft are expected to be vigilant about the drones near aerodromes as part of standard flight safety protocol (EASA 2021). From 2021 through 2022, there have been 63 drone incidents as reported by the US Government Accountability Office (GAO) where pilots had to take evasive actions, including four commercial aircraft as well (GAO 2024).

A 7-year-old boy underwent open heart surgery after being hit by a light show drone that lost control in Orlando, US, on 21 December 2024 (Fox News 2024a, 2024b, NTSB 2024a). Another incident took place on 15 January 2021 in Sydney, Australia, where a drone collided with a hotel window due to loss of control, injuring an occupant, after its compass failed due to electromagnetic interference. Between 2017 to 2020, 94 occurrences of similar nature were reported in Australia, most of which resulted in damage to property (ATSB 2021, DJI 2025a). ICAO encourages states to pursue a whole-of-government strategy for their respective drone industry, by consulting and engaging with the key stakeholders, both aviation and non-aviation, to develop effective regulatory framework. According to ICAO, the most effective strategy for the enforcement of drone regulations is to ensure that all drones are registered (ICAO 2021g). The organisations shaping drone regulations in the EU include EASA, European National Aviation Authorities, European Organisation for Civil Aviation Equipment, EUROCONTROL (a pan-European, civil–military organisation), Joint Authorities for Rulemaking on Unmanned Systems, Single European Sky Air Traffic Management Research Joint Undertaking, and European Defence Agency (EASA 2025d, EUROCONTROL 2025).

EASA requires drone operators to undergo appropriate training (EASA 2025b). In the US, all recreational drone users are mandated to pass the Recreational UAS Safety Test, while non-recreational or commercial operations are regulated under FAA Part 107 (FAA 2025a). According to Civil Aviation Safety Authority Australia, a Remote Pilot Licence is not mandatory for recreational drone users (Civil Aviation Safety Authority 2025). However, in response to a sharp rise in drone-related incidents, including unauthorised operations, Japan implemented mandatory registration for all drones and model aircraft weighing 100 grams or more, effective from 20 June 2022 (MLIT Japan 2022).

DAA technologies for drones remain one of the primary areas of research for the FAA (FAA 2025b). In 2024, following a series of trials, Transport Canada also concluded that DAA technology is not yet reliable and requires further standardisation. Additionally, it was emphasised that technology cannot achieve its full safety potential in isolation; a comprehensive system supported by a robust regulatory framework is essential (Government of Canada 2024).

According to the US Forest Service, drones equipped with appropriate cameras and sensors can assist or even replace the firefighting efforts by manned aircraft in night operations, or during low visibility, where it could be risky to utilise manned aircraft (US Department of Agriculture 2022). In addition, drones used for surveillance, reconnaissance, and targeted strikes in military operations, can be flown remotely at no risk to the pilot, thereby preserving human lives and maintaining optimal performance without the limitations of human endurance

(Australian Army Research Centre 2024).

The Extended Minimum Crew Operations – Single Pilot Operations (eMCO-SiPO) project for commercial aircraft launched by EASA to explore the possibility of reducing the number of pilots on commercial passenger aircraft, was initiated as a result of the continued technological advancements including the development of autonomous drones (EASA 2025e). According to a recent study, technological advancements in the drone industry have outpaced existing regulatory frameworks, leading to operations that often fall outside traditional regulatory boundaries. The authors emphasised that ongoing collaboration with industry stakeholders is essential to ensure the safe and accountable integration of drones into the civilian airspace (Shenoy and Tyagi 2022).

4.2.2 Aviation Safety Strategies and Drones

The GASP 2023–2025 addresses proactive management of emerging issues by outlining a reporting mechanism for States and industry stakeholders, enabling ICAO to conduct a data-driven analysis and consider the reported issues as operational safety risks. In addition, ICAO encourages States and industry stakeholders to adopt new technologies, procedures, and operational practices to mitigate the risks associated with these emerging challenges (ICAO 2022b).

Asia–Pacific RASP (AP–RASP) 2023–2025 identifies UAS as an emerging risk (ICAO 2023c). Africa–Indian Ocean RASP (AFI–RASP) 2023–2025 also identifies drone operations near aerodromes as an emerging issue. Two different expansions of the acronym UAS appear in AFI–RASP 2023–2025, Unmanned Aircraft Systems and Unmanned Aerial Systems (ICAO 2023d).

Middle East RASP (MID–RASP) 2023–2025 highlights the risks drones pose to manned aviation and underscores the role of both manned and unmanned aircraft operators in risk mitigation. It acknowledges the limited aviation background among drone professionals, recommends early stakeholder involvement in regulatory development, and supports the use of ICAO Doc 10088 on civil–military cooperation (ICAO 2023b).

The North American, Central American and Caribbean RASP (NACC RASP) 2021 does not address drones (ICAO 2021h). In contrast, the South American Region Safety Plan (SAMSP) 2023–2025 emphasises the identification of potential safety risks, collection of relevant data, and proactive development of mitigations related to drone operations near aerodromes. The acronyms UAS and RPAS appear in the SAMSP without explanation of their full forms (ICAO 2023e).

The EUR RASP 2023–2025 emphasises the need for a regulatory framework to support safe drone operations, facilitating manufacturer design and operator compliance. It includes objectives from EASA’s C-UAS Action Plan, and highlights the importance of civil–military cooperation, recommending full application of ICAO Doc 10088 in line with the principle “as civil as possible–as military as necessary”, while acknowledging that such cooperation can be improved only within individual States (ICAO and EASA 2023).

The EPAS 2023–2025 includes objectives from the C-UAS Action Plan and confirms continued support for the EC’s Drone Strategy 2.0 to address safety and cybersecurity. It emphasises enhanced civil–military cooperation for regulatory development to benefit from military experience and expertise, and outlines plans to improve training and examinations for drone maintenance personnel (EASA 2023b).

Australian NASP 2024–2027 identifies drones as an emerging threat to aviation safety and outlines ongoing efforts to develop a reporting mechanism, conduct safety campaigns for recreational flyers, and enhance drone detection around aerodromes (Commonwealth of Australia 2024).

China NASP 2021–2025 identifies the expansion of the drone industry as an emerging risk. It prioritises collaboration with stakeholders to develop a regulatory framework for drones, establish a real-time operational data platform, and optimise the safety oversight mechanism. It also emphasises continuous improvement in drone airworthiness certification and personnel technical proficiency (Civil Aviation Administration of China 2022).

India NASP 2024–2028 focuses on the safe operation of the drone industry and highlights near-term drone application areas such as agriculture, mapping, road and railway surveying, mining, aerial filming, and surveillance. It outlines ongoing efforts for global regulatory harmonisation, including aspects related to unauthorised drone operations. It also includes plans for monitoring and updating regulations, developing harmonised standards for critical UAS components, and implementing remote identification and tracking. The acronym RPAS appears in the Glossary section but is not used in the main text (DGCA India 2024).

Sierra Leone NASP 2022–2026 identifies drones as an emerging safety issue and highlights plans for monitoring existing regulations, coordinating with other agencies, and developing internationally harmonised regulations, including those for small drones. Near-term drone application areas include medicine, agriculture, construction, surveying, roads, railway, mining, aerial filming, and forest and environment study (Sierra Leone CAA 2022).

Iran NASP 2024–2026 identifies drones as an emerging safety issue. It highlights the risk of frequency interference when multiple drones operate in the same area, and the need for precise flight management to avoid airspace congestion near aerodromes. Mitigating actions planned in coordination with the military include allocation of dedicated frequency bands, international cooperation for harmonised regulations, operator training, and measures to distribute drone activity more evenly across operational areas (CAA of Islamic Republic of Iran 2024).

The UAE NASP 2024–2026 identifies drones operating near airports as an emerging issue based on safety trend analysis reports. It includes initiatives to enhance oversight capabilities, including the development of processes and technical capacities in collaboration with industry stakeholders. The acronym UAS is referenced in the main text but is not included in the list of acronyms or explained within the document (GCAA 2024).

The current edition of US NASP includes website links to drone-related safety initiatives on the FAA’s website. It also states that the FAA is working to enable the safe integration of airspace users and provides a link to a webpage outlining major drone integration initiatives (FAA 2022b, 2025c). Jamaica NASP 2024–2026 identifies drones as an emerging issue, particularly near aerodromes, and sets a target to implement drone regulations aligned with ICAO standards (Jamaica CAA 2024).

Finland NASP 2023–2025 acknowledges risks associated with the rapid growth of the drone industry and highlights limited regulatory awareness and safety culture among drone operators as key safety concerns. It outlines a plan for drone tracking and refers to awareness campaigns conducted and planned to promote safety within the drone sector (Finnish Transport and Communications Agency Traficom 2023). The UK NASP 2022–2024 identifies Military Aviation Authority as a key stakeholder and drone integration is listed among national

operational safety risks, with key risk areas including mid-air collisions with commercial air transport and loss of control over the public (UK CAA 2022).

Drones have not been addressed in Bhutan NASP 2023–2025, Cyprus State Safety Plan 2022, Estonian State Plan for Aviation Safety (SPAS) 2020–2024, Ethiopia NASP 2023–2025, Guyana NASP 2021–2022, Icelandic Plan for Aviation Safety (IPAS) 2023–2025, Indonesia NASP 2024–2026, Italian SPAS 2021–2025, Kazakhstan Aviation Safety Plan (KASP) 2024–2027, Lebanon NASP 2021–2025, Maldives NASP 2020–2022, Pakistan NASP 2022–2024, Philippines NASP 2022–2025, Rwanda NASP 2021–2025, and the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia (KSA) NASP 2025–2027 (ICAO 2025).

4.2.3 Human Factors in Drone Operations and their Effects on Aviation Safety

The probable cause of the mid-air collision between a Robinson R44 helicopter and DJI Mavic 2 PRO drone on 30 December 2023 near Daytona Beach Airport, Florida, US, was attributed to the drone operator’s failure to comply with the altitude limitations, but findings of the final report by the NTSB also indicate issues with the helicopter pilot’s decision-making/judgment and knowledge of procedures. It has also been analysed in the report that the drone operator was unaware before the flight that he would exceed the altitude limitation by 30 feet (Aviation Safety Network 2024, NTSB 2024b).

According to an Airbus press release issued on 29 June 2020, the Autonomous Taxi, Take-Off and Landing (ATTOL) project was completed after more than 500 test flights were conducted over a period of two years. The project achieved autonomous taxiing, take-off, and landing of commercial aircraft, demonstrating that the technology could assist pilots in flight operations by enabling greater focus on strategic decision-making and mission management, thereby contributing to aircraft safety (Airbus 2020).

According to the FAA, automation enhances flight precision and accuracy, but it is essential to understand its limitations to effectively intervene when manual control is needed. A malfunctioning sensor can result in erroneous automated system responses, and excessive reliance on automation may contribute to boredom and complacency due to which automation errors may be overlooked. As per the FAA Human Factors Design Standard (HF-STD-001B), automation is often intended to reduce the workload, but this is not always the result because users of automated systems may experience higher levels of mental workload due to constant monitoring tasks which can also lead to decreased alertness. Intermittent periods of manual control during which automation is suspended can help minimise complacency, enhance vigilance, and allow better recovery from failure. Training on automated systems enables users to develop an informed understanding of the system's reliability under varying operational conditions (FAA 2016, 2022c).

According to EASA AI Roadmap 2.0, the stepwise integration of AI in aviation aims to enhance the reliability of autonomous drone operations. Currently, this integration emphasises a human-centric approach, with considerations for full autonomy planned for future regulatory evaluation (EASA 2023c). EASA has also published templates of the Operations Manuals for UAS which include sections on checklists and maintenance procedures (EASA 2023d). Similarly, ASTM International (formerly the American Society for Testing and Materials) has developed several standards related to UAS, including the Standard Specification for General Maintenance Manual (GMM) for a small UAS (sUAS), the Standard Specification for Unmanned Aircraft Flight Manual (UFM) for UAS, and the Standard Guide for UAS

Maintenance Technician Qualification (ASTM 2019, 2023a, 2023b, 2025a, 2025b).

4.2.4 Best Practices and Policies for Safe Expansion of the Drone Industry

The MQ-9A Reaper RPA, also known as Predator B, has an MTOM of 4,763 kilograms, a service ceiling of 50,000 feet, and an endurance of up to 27 hours. It is currently operated from Syracuse Hancock International Airport, New York, US, which had a total passenger traffic of 3,004,937 in 2024 and 2,856,038 in 2023. According to 2020 data, more than 6,000 military operations involving Predator B were conducted annually from this airport. Between 1 January and 28 February 2025, the airport recorded 43,722 aircraft movements, of which 3,504 were military operations (General Atomics Aeronautical 2025, Syracuse Regional Airport Authority 2020, 2025a, 2025b).

On 25 June 2020, a Predator B crashed shortly after takeoff at Syracuse Hancock International Airport. The aircraft sustained significant damage, and a portion of airport runway lights were also damaged, but there were no injuries or fatalities reported. The cause of the accident was the remote pilot's action of pulling the Condition Lever instead of pushing the Flap Lever, which resulted in the fuel supply to the engine being cut off. The contributing factor was the design of the Condition Lever and Flap Lever being in close proximity, combined with the absence of markings, colour differentiation, or a safety guard (US Air Force 2021).

According to EASA Part-66 (Maintenance Certifying Staff), maintenance personnel for manned aircraft are licensed under various categories, including Category A, B1, B2, B2L, B3, C, and L. These categories are further subdivided into specific ratings such as A1, A2, A3, A4, B1.1, B1.2, B1.3, B1.4, L1, L1C, L2, L2C, L3H, L3G, L4H, L4G, and L5, depending on the aircraft type and associated subsystems (EASA 2025f).

In accordance with EASA Regulations (EU) 2019/947 and 2019/945, a Remote Pilot Certificate of Competency is required to operate a drone in Subcategory A2 (which permits flight close to people) within the risk-based Open category of drone operations. The other subcategories include A1 (permitting flight over people, but not over assemblies) and A3 (requiring operations to be conducted far from people), both of which require only a proof of completion of the online training (EASA 2025g). For operations within the Specific category, an operational authorisation must be obtained from the national competent authority. The Certified category is intended to encompass emerging applications such as drone taxis, with a regulatory approach closely aligned with that of conventional manned aviation (EASA 2025b, 2025h, 2025i, 2025j).

According to the FAA, the primary Aviation Mechanic Certificate ratings include Airframe and Powerplant, but a combined Airframe and Powerplant certificate may also be obtained (FAA 2024). The FAA Part 107 governs Remote Pilot Certification with an sUAS rating, which requires passing an initial aeronautical knowledge test and completing recurrent trainings. The training also covers maintenance and preflight inspection procedures. This regulation applies to drones weighing less than 55 pounds and restricts their operation to a maximum allowable altitude of 400 feet (FAA 2020, National Archives and Records Administration 2025).

5. Findings

5.1 Impact of Drones on Aviation Safety

Experts identified the potential for drones to cause ground injuries, fatalities, and property damage, along with the risk of mid-air encounters with manned aircraft. Secondary data reported similar incidents in Orlando and Sydney involving injuries and damage on the ground. The GAO and ATSB documented multiple cases in the US and Australia, respectively, where drones prompted pilot evasive action and caused property damage (ATSB 2021, DJI 2025a, Fox News 2024a, 2024b, NTSB 2024a). EASA has already recommended pilots of manned aircraft to remain vigilant near aerodromes due to increased drone activity (EASA 2021).

Experts noted that drone technology influenced the concept of single-pilot commercial cockpits and enabled the replacement of manned aircraft in high-risk roles. Likewise, the secondary data indicated the use of drones by the US Forest Service to assist or replace manned aircraft in wildfire response during hazardous or low-visibility conditions (US Department of Agriculture 2022). The Australian Army Research Centre also reported reduced pilot risk through drone use in military operations (Australian Army Research Centre 2024). Furthermore, EASA linked the eMCO-SiPO project to advancements in autonomous drone technology (EASA 2025e).

Experts recommended a robust and adaptive regulatory framework developed through cross-sector collaboration to effectively manage the negative as well as the positive impacts of drones on aviation safety. Similarly, the secondary data implied that ICAO promoted a whole-of-government approach (ICAO 2021g), while joint civil–military institutions contributed to EU drone regulations (EASA 2025d, EUROCONTROL 2025). Industrial collaboration was also identified as essential for safe drone integration in a recent study (Shenoy and Tyagi 2022). Moreover, MID–RASP 2023–2025 advised early stakeholder involvement (ICAO 2023b), and Sierra Leone NASP 2022–2026 emphasised inter-agency coordination in regulatory development (Sierra Leone CAA 2022).

5.2 Aviation Safety Strategies and Drones

One expert identified low-risk areas including agriculture and mapping as suitable for near-term drone applications. Secondary data from India NASP 2024–2028 and Sierra Leone NASP 2022–2026 listed similar priority sectors, including agriculture, mapping, surveying, mining, filming, and environmental studies (DGCA India 2024, Sierra Leone CAA 2022). Another expert highlighted the need to allocate dedicated frequency bands for drones and raised concerns about signal interference near high-power transmissions. Iran NASP 2024–2026 noted similar frequency interference risks in drone operations and proposed dedicated frequency allocation (CAA of Islamic Republic of Iran 2024).

5.3 Human Factors in Drone Operations and their Effects on Aviation Safety

Experts identified a knowledge gap between manned and unmanned aviation professionals as a safety risk in shared airspace. They highlighted limited awareness of safety protocols among drone operators, often due to non-aviation backgrounds. This concern was reflected in MID–RASP 2023–2025 and Finland NASP 2023–2025, which noted low regulatory awareness and weak safety culture among drone professionals (Finnish Transport and Communications Agency Traficom 2023, ICAO 2023b).

Experts identified human error by manned aircraft pilots and poor planning by drone operators as factors increasing mid-air collision risks. Secondary data from the NTSB’s report on a

drone–helicopter collision in Daytona Beach noted altitude unawareness by the drone operator and procedural deficiencies on part of the helicopter pilot (Aviation Safety Network 2024, NTSB 2024a). MID–RASP 2023–2025 also highlighted the shared role of manned and unmanned operators in risk mitigation (ICAO 2023b).

Experts considered human judgment more effective than autonomous drone systems in complex scenarios. Similarly, the FAA underscored the need for human intervention due to automation limitations (FAA 2022c), and the EASA AI Roadmap 2.0 advocated for a stepwise, human-centric AI integration approach (EASA 2023c).

To address the human factors, experts recommended comprehensive training for both manned and unmanned aviation personnel. They emphasised the prioritisation of system management, emergency response, and air traffic coordination over manual control tasks in drone training. FAA HF-STD-001B similarly linked automated systems training to improved system understanding but highlighted the role of manual control in maintaining vigilance (FAA 2016). One expert identified the lack of HMI standardisation as a latent error, complicating system transitions and increasing training needs. Secondary data on the Predator B crash at Syracuse Hancock Airport identified design flaws as one of the contributing factors (US Air Force 2021). Experts also viewed non-standardised manuals, tied to limited aviation knowledge among some manufacturers, as an additional latent risk. According to secondary data, EASA provided UAS manual templates (EASA 2023d) and ASTM International developed sUAS standards for UFM and GMM (ASTM 2019, 2023a, 2025a).

5.4 Best Practices and Policies for Safe Expansion of the Drone Industry

One expert shared a best practice involving the development of operational procedures in collaboration with regulators for drones with an MTOM of 50–100 kilograms, enabling safe military operations near an international airport without disrupting civil air traffic. Secondary data reported that Predator B drones (MTOM of 4,763 kilograms) operate from Syracuse Hancock International Airport, which recorded 3,504 military operations between 1 January and 28 February 2025 (General Atomics Aeronautical 2025, Syracuse Regional Airport Authority 2020, 2025b). A Predator B crash on 25 June 2020 caused severe damage to the drone and minor damage to the infrastructure of Syracuse Hancock Airport, with no injuries or fatalities reported (US Air Force 2021). In addition, joint civil–military institutions were noted as influencing EU drone regulations (EASA 2025d, EUROCONTROL 2025). MID–RASP 2023–2025 and EUR RASP 2023–2025 also supported the use of ICAO Doc 10088 to guide civil–military cooperation in regulatory development (ICAO 2023b, ICAO and EASA 2023). EPAS 2023–2025 emphasised enhanced civil–military collaboration (EASA 2023b), and Iran NASP 2024–2026 highlighted mitigation actions coordinated with the military (CAA of Islamic Republic of Iran 2024).

Experts recommended category-specific and safety-focused operator training, standardisation of critical UAS components, drone tracking mechanisms, promotion of drone use in low-risk sectors, and dedicated licensing for drone engineers and technicians. In the secondary data, EASA outlined category-specific training requirements, pilot certification, and operational authorisations under Regulations (EU) 2019/947 and 2019/945 (EASA 2025b, 2025h, 2025i, 2025j). FAA Part 107 was identified as the framework for sUAS under 55 pounds (FAA 2020, National Archives and Records Administration 2025). India NASP 2024–2028 planned harmonised standards for critical UAS components, implementing remote tracking, and

promoting near-term applications such as agriculture and mapping (DGCA India 2024). China NASP 2021–2025 prioritised stakeholder collaboration for real-time drone data (Civil Aviation Administration of China 2022), and Sierra Leone NASP 2022–2026 listed application areas including medicine, agriculture, and environmental monitoring (Sierra Leone CAA 2022). ASTM International was reported to have developed a standard for UAS Maintenance Technician Qualification (ASTM 2023b).

5.5 Summary of Findings

The findings revealed a strong alignment between expert perspectives and the secondary data. However, a minor divergence was noted in training priorities, where experts downplayed manual control skills, while documentary evidence highlighted their role in safety. In addition, the expert perspective on inter-drone operation management in low-risk application areas was not addressed in the secondary data.

6. Analysis

6.1 Impact of Drones on Aviation Safety

The negative impacts of drones on aviation safety extend beyond mid-air encounter risks with manned aircraft and also include ground-related risks, which may result in injuries, fatalities, or property damage (EASA 2021). FAA Advisory Circular (AC) 107-2A reinforces this view by categorising any drone crash that results in property damage of US dollars (USD) 500 or more as a reportable accident (FAA 2021).

Drones also contribute positively to aviation safety. They are not only replacing conventional aviation in high-risk civil and military operations (Australian Army Research Centre 2024, US Department of Agriculture 2022), but their technologically advanced and mature systems can also be adapted for use on manned platforms to enhance aviation safety. EASA's eMCO-SiPO project is a notable example of a regulatory initiative inspired by drone technology to support single-pilot operations (EASA 2025e), whose technical feasibility has already been demonstrated through the ATTOL project by Airbus (Airbus 2020).

A set of well-structured regulations developed in close collaboration with all relevant stakeholders, including both aviation and non-aviation sectors and particularly involving military personnel with experience in both manned and unmanned aircraft, is essential to mitigate the negative impacts of drones on aviation safety and to harness their positive potential. While the advancement of technological solutions such as DAA systems is critical, a comprehensive system-wide approach is equally important. It may include public awareness campaigns, robust enforcement mechanisms such as mandatory registration of all drones regardless of weight, and standardised training for both manned and unmanned aviation professionals (EASA 2025d, EUROCONTROL 2025, ICAO 2021g).

6.2 Aviation Safety Strategies and Drones (SWOT Analysis)

6.2.1 Strengths

The GASP 2023–2025 advises States and industry stakeholders to proactively manage emerging issues through structured mechanisms. In addition, it encourages the adoption of new technologies, procedures, and operational practices to mitigate the risks associated with these emerging challenges (ICAO 2022a).

6.2.2 Weaknesses

The GASP 2023–2025 does not explicitly address drones, indicating a gap in the global strategy for integrating UAS into aviation safety planning (ICAO 2022a).

6.2.3 Opportunities

The current editions of AP-RASP, AFI-RASP, MID-RASP, SAMSP, and the NASPs of Australia, China, Sierra Leone, Iran, UAE, Jamaica, and Finland explicitly identify drones as an emerging risk. MID-RASP underscores the role of both manned and unmanned aircraft operators in mitigating drone-related risks (ICAO 2023b, 2023c, 2023d, 2023e, 2025). EPAS 2023–2025 emphasises enhanced civil–military cooperation, aiming for drone regulations to benefit from military experience in UAS operations (EASA 2023a). The UK NASP 2022–2024 also identifies military as a key stakeholder (UK CAA 2022). Australian NASP 2024–2027 highlights the efforts to enhance drone detection around aerodromes (Commonwealth of Australia 2024). India NASP 2024–2028 and Sierra Leone NASP 2022–2026 include agriculture, mapping, surveying, mining, and aerial filming as near-term drone application areas (DGCA India 2024, Sierra Leone CAA 2022).

6.2.4 Threats

Drones have not been addressed in the current editions of the NACC RASP and in the NASPs for Bhutan, Cyprus, Estonia (SPAS), Ethiopia, Guyana, Iceland (IPAS), Indonesia, Italy (SPAS), Kazakhstan (KASP), Lebanon, Maldives, Pakistan, Philippines, Rwanda, and KSA (ICAO 2021h, 2025). Additionally, the current editions of SAMSP, India NASP, and UAE NASP show inconsistencies in the use and definition of key terms such as UAS and RPAS (DGCA India 2024, GCAA 2024, ICAO 2023e).

6.3 Human Factors in Drone Operations and their Effects on Aviation Safety

Human factors have both positive and negative impacts on drone operations, with corresponding implications for aviation safety. Errors in planning, communication, and decision-making can compromise the safety of even autonomous drones, which are generally considered safer than those with limited or no autonomy (Airbus 2020). The drone-helicopter accident at Daytona Beach illustrates the consequences of human errors of similar nature, as the drone operator failed to assess whether the planned mission would exceed the permitted altitude, which contributed to the collision (Aviation Safety Network 2024, NTSB 2024b).

In contrast, sound human judgment can help overcome the current limitations of autonomous drone operations, particularly in complex scenarios where human decision-making may outperform automated systems. This can contribute to the enhancement of aviation safety (FAA 2016, 2022c). This interpretation is supported by the probable cause of the collision between an Uber autonomous vehicle and a pedestrian on 18 March 2018 in the US. Due to the limitations in the autonomous system of the vehicle coupled with the lack of vigilance on the part of the vehicle operator, a 49-year-old pedestrian was fatally injured as the autonomous vehicle struck her while she was crossing the road (NTSB 2019). In addition to active errors, latent errors can also adversely affect drone operations. For instance, non-standardised HMI designs may increase the likelihood of operator error, as seen in the Predator B crash at Syracuse Hancock Airport (US Air Force 2021).

Effective management of the dual impacts of human factors in drone operations and their direct influence on aviation safety requires that comprehensive and standardised training for both manned and unmanned aviation professionals be treated as an absolute priority. ICAO Annex 19 (Safety Management) and Doc 9859 (Safety Management Manual) clearly define the framework for a Safety Management System, comprising four components and twelve elements. One of these components is safety promotion, and its first element is training and education (ICAO 2016, 2017, 2018).

While standardised training is essential to mitigate both active and latent errors in drone operations, it is equally imperative that manufacturers adhere to the existing industry guidelines when preparing drone manuals and checklists. In addition, regular feedback must be solicited from drone operators to ensure that these documents remain relevant, practical, and subject to continuous improvement. Collaborative engagement with regulatory authorities and standards organisations is essential, as the true effectiveness of these guidelines can only be validated through their widespread and consistent implementation across the industry (ASTM 2019, 2023a, 2025a, EASA 2023d).

6.4 Best Practices and Policies for Safe Expansion of the Drone Industry

Predator B operations from Syracuse Hancock Airport offer a valuable case study for identifying best practices to support a safe expansion of the drone industry (Syracuse Regional

Airport Authority 2020, 2025a, 2025b). This example underscores the importance of enhanced civil–military collaboration. The military’s role is particularly critical, as military aviation personnel remain the most experienced professionals in unmanned aviation, generally with unmatched qualifications and operational expertise (Schmidt et al. 2021). Furthermore, the established reporting systems used in manned aviation, along with well-defined procedures for safety investigations and follow-ups, can be adopted as best practices to strengthen the safety framework for drone operations.

To ensure a safe expansion of the drone industry, it is recommended that aviation regulatory authorities actively engage with industry stakeholders to develop harmonised policies, regulations, standards, and procedures. Robust systems should be established for the efficient tracking of drones to support timely investigations and the formulation of safety recommendations following incidents or accidents. In addition to standardising certifications, licensing, and operational authorisations for drone operators (EASA 2025b, 2025g, 2025h, 2025i, 2025j, FAA 2020, National Archives and Records Administration 2025), it is essential that maintenance personnel in the drone industry are also certified or licensed through a structured and harmonised framework, similar to practices in manned aviation (EASA 2025f, FAA 2024). A structured framework for licensing and certification of aviation maintenance personnel enhances their competencies which ensures aviation safety (Timjerdine et al. 2024). As an immediate policy priority, the use of drones should be promoted in sectors that pose minimal risk to manned aviation. These include, but are not limited to, agriculture, aerial filming, surveying, and mapping.

7. Discussion

7.1 Impact of Drones on Aviation Safety

The ground-related risks involve property damage due to drone crashes which must be reported in accordance with FAA AC 107-2A for damages of USD 500 or more (FAA 2021). The practical implementation of this clause could present complexities if damage assessment process is not regulated. In addition, a drone crash could cause property damage of less than USD 500 and still be significant from a safety standpoint; it can be a near miss that could have resulted in a fatality. All similar loopholes are most likely to be addressed if all drones are registered through an extremely simplified registration process, requiring minimal time and effort, to ensure compliance.

Given that DAA technology is not yet fully mature (Government of Canada 2024), a practical interim measure could be the widespread integration of ADS-B In systems in drones. ADS-B In is a lightweight and cost-effective solution that can significantly enhance situational awareness by enabling drones to detect nearby manned aircraft equipped with ADS-B Out. While it does not provide autonomous avoidance capability, it can enhance situational awareness and support safer operations by allowing drone operators or onboard systems to take timely action. As regulatory frameworks continue to evolve, ADS-B Out requirements could also be introduced for all manned aircraft and certain categories of drones (DJI 2025b, FAA 2023, uAvionix 2019a, 2019b, 2020, 2024).

7.2 Aviation Safety Strategies and Drones

Based on the SWOT and TOWS analysis attached as Appendix A, four strategic options have been selected and are presented below as retrieved from the TOWS matrix:

- Promote the inclusion of drones in future editions of GASP using standardised terminology to address the current omission and help mitigate inconsistencies in definitions across existing national and regional safety plans (Weakness–Threat Strategy).
- Utilise the emphasis in the MID–RASP on shared responsibility of manned and unmanned aircraft operators to inform and support the inclusion of drone-specific risks and mitigation strategies in future updates of GASP (Weakness–Opportunity Strategy).
- Leverage the recognition of near-term drone applications such as agriculture, mapping, surveying, mining, and aerial filming in the NASPs of India and Sierra Leone to promote the inclusion of drone-specific operational contexts and associated safety considerations in future editions of GASP, thereby addressing its current omission and aligning global strategy with emerging practical use cases (Weakness–Opportunity Strategy).
- Leverage the emphasis on civil–military cooperation in the EPAS and UK NASP to support the inclusion of drone-related safety considerations in future editions of GASP, drawing on military expertise in UAS operations to address the current omission (Weakness–Opportunity Strategy).

7.3 Human Factors in Drone Operations and their Effects on Aviation Safety

Human factors in drone operations are directly related to both manned aircraft pilots and the drone operators, with additional risks emerging from skill-based errors by the maintenance

personnel and latent errors due to the lapses in the documentation by the drone manufacturers (Grindley et al. 2024b, ICAO 2023b, Nicklin 2022, NTSB 2024b, Sameera, Bindra, and Rath 2021) . Without imparting a comprehensive and standardised training, drone operations in shared airspace are likely to continue posing threats to aviation safety.

Another critical challenge is the standardisation of HMI designs in drones because of the wide variation in drone categories (Kille et al. 2021, Telli et al. 2023, US Air Force 2021). The absence of globally standardised drone categorisation also complicates the creation of structured training programs and licensing systems for unmanned aviation. Without internationally harmonised drone classifications, training and regulatory frameworks are likely to remain fragmented.

A practical step forward may involve improving the standardisation and regulatory oversight of drone documentation, including maintenance and operational manuals. Manufacturers could be mandated to align with internationally recognised standards, such as those established by EASA and ASTM International (ASTM 2025a, EASA 2023d). While structured operator feedback can support continuous improvement, effective implementation will depend on strong regulatory oversight and enforcement.

7.4 Best Practices and Policies for Safe Expansion of the Drone Industry

In the context of timely investigations and the issuance of safety recommendations, the NTSB's final report on the Daytona Beach mid-air collision between drone and helicopter was published within a month of the accident. Although the findings of the report highlighted issues related to both the helicopter pilot and the drone operator, it did not include any safety recommendations (NTSB 2024b). Given that mid-air collisions are a recognised risk area in drone operations (Osiecki, Cyran, and Dębowski 2024), and in light of documented concerns such as low regulatory awareness and weak safety culture among drone operators (Finnish Transport and Communications Agency Traficom 2023), the inclusion of targeted recommendations could have strengthened the report's role in enhancing aviation safety. As a Class 4 investigation, the investigator-in-charge had the opportunity to collaborate with industry stakeholders to develop practical strategies addressing the identified safety issues, potentially reducing the risk of similar occurrences in the future (NTSB 2024c).

8. Conclusions

8.1 Impact of Drones on Aviation Safety

Unlike previous studies that primarily focus on the risk of mid-air collisions between drones and manned aircraft, this research highlights that ground-related risks, including injuries, fatalities, and property damage also pose a significant safety concern. The research has also identified positive impacts of drones, including their use as replacements for manned aircraft in high-risk civil and military operations. Furthermore, drone-driven innovations in manned aviation, such as the development of single-pilot cockpit concepts, have also been presented. Mitigating the risks and maximising the benefits of drones requires well-structured regulations developed with the input from both civil and military stakeholders. In addition to technological solutions such as DAA systems, a comprehensive approach that includes public awareness, mandatory drone registration, and standardised training is essential for ensuring aviation safety.

8.2 Aviation Safety Strategies and Drones

Proactive management of emerging aviation safety challenges and encouraging the adoption of innovative technologies and practices are the strengths of GASP 2023–2025. However, a key weakness in the global strategy for aviation safety is that drones are not explicitly addressed in the GASP. Opportunities exist through various regional and national plans that recognise drones as an emerging risk, support civil–military collaboration, and highlight diverse drone applications in areas such as agriculture, mapping, and aerial filming. Nonetheless, threats persist due to the lack of drone-related content in several safety plans and inconsistencies in the use of key terms, which may hinder effective global harmonisation.

One strategic option is to address the omission of drones in future editions of GASP and avoid inconsistent use of terminology in future editions of all aviation safety plans. Other options involve addressing the current omission of drones in the GASP by leveraging opportunities highlighted in regional and national plans to inform future updates. These include promoting shared responsibilities between manned and unmanned aircraft operators, enhancing civil–military cooperation to incorporate military UAS expertise, and integrating sector-specific applications such as agriculture, mapping, surveying, mining, and aerial filming as near-term priorities.

8.3 Human Factors in Drone Operations and their Effects on Aviation Safety

Human factors in drone operations are not limited to unmanned aviation professionals; errors by manned aviation personnel, particularly pilots, can also lead to drone-related accidents. Mid-air collision risks are heightened due to poor planning by drone operators as well as because of errors by manned aircraft pilots, underscoring the shared responsibility for safety. On the contrary, consistent with existing research, sound human judgment can outperform automation in complex scenarios, helping to mitigate current limitations of autonomous drone operations and enhance aviation safety.

Additional concerns include low regulatory awareness and weak safety culture among drone operators along with latent risks from non-standardised manuals due to limited aviation knowledge among drone manufacturers. Addressing these issues requires comprehensive and standardised training for both manned and unmanned aviation professionals, as well as improved documentation practices aligned with established guidelines. Continuous operator feedback and strong regulatory oversight are essential to ensure aviation safety.

8.4 Best Practices and Policies for Safe Expansion of the Drone Industry

Military aviation personnel, with their extensive experience and expertise in unmanned aviation, play a critical role in supporting the safe expansion of the drone industry. Predator B operations from Syracuse Hancock Airport provide a valuable case study highlighting the success story of civil–military collaboration. Established reporting systems and well-defined safety investigation procedures from manned aviation can also serve as best practices for strengthening the safety framework in drone operations.

The research concludes that regulatory harmonisation, stakeholder engagement, and structured certification frameworks for both drone operators and maintenance personnel are essential for ensuring safe drone integration. Emphasis should also be placed on encouraging drone use in low-risk sectors such as agriculture and mapping to minimise safety concerns and foster sustainable growth. Strengthening tracking mechanisms for drone operations is also necessary to support timely investigations and the development of effective safety recommendations.

9. Recommendations

9.1 Introduction

Although many of the recommendations presented across the thematic sections in this chapter are policy-oriented and contribute to the safe expansion of the drone industry; those outlined in Section 9.5.2 are specifically evidence-based policy recommendations derived from best practices identified during the course of this research.

9.2 Impact of Drones on Aviation Safety

Drone registration should be made mandatory for all categories of drones to support the reliable collection of occurrence data, including both mid-air and ground-related incidents and accidents. To facilitate widespread compliance, the registration process should be streamlined and accessible; mandatory registration at the point of sale through authorised vendors could further ensure compliance and traceability.

In addition to their use in high-risk civil and military operations, drones should also be promoted for routine low-risk applications, particularly where they offer more economical solutions. As manned aviation adopts drone-driven innovations such as the single-pilot cockpit concept, drones should likewise integrate proven and feasible manned aviation technologies. In this context, ADS-B should be mandated for drones that pose a higher risk to manned aircraft as an interim safety measure until other technological solutions are fully mature and deemed feasible. Finally, to support safe and coordinated integration of drones into the airspace system, efforts should be initiated at the state, regional, and global levels to standardise and harmonise drone-related technology, training, and regulations through close collaboration with all industry stakeholders, including the military.

9.3 Aviation Safety Strategies and Drones

It is recommended that ICAO considers recognising drones as a key risk to aviation in future editions of the GASP, using consistent and standardised terminology, while also encouraging the safe use of drones in application areas that do not pose a direct threat to aviation safety. In addition, ICAO should make efforts to ensure that all NASPs are available in English on its official website to support global accessibility and regulatory coherence. Furthermore, ICAO should encourage States that currently do not address drones to consider incorporating them into their respective safety plans, in alignment with their national priorities and regulatory readiness. ICAO should also exercise its coordinating role to facilitate the inclusion of drone-related risks in the upcoming editions of the NACC RASP (ICAO 2021f, 2021i, 2022a).

9.4 Human Factors in Drone Operations and their Effects on Aviation Safety

In order to effectively manage human factors in drone operations and their implications for aviation safety, it is recommended that standardised and appropriate training be provided to professionals across both the manned and unmanned aviation sectors. Additionally, aviation regulatory authorities should ensure that drone manufacturers provide a complete set of standardised manuals and documentation, supported by a structured feedback mechanism that enables timely updates based on operator input.

9.5 Best Practices and Policies for Safe Expansion of the Drone Industry

9.5.1 Best Practices

The involvement of military aviation personnel, particularly those with experience and expertise in both manned and unmanned aircraft, is likely to enhance the effectiveness of drone-related policies, regulations, standards, and procedures. Additionally, the adoption of reporting

systems and safety investigation procedures from manned aviation within the drone industry can contribute to the identification of safety issues and support proactive learning, allowing the drone sector to benefit from established aviation practices without experiencing the same level of loss that historically drove safety improvements in manned aviation (ICAO 2022a, Our World in Data 2024).

9.5.2 Policy Recommendations

Aviation regulatory authorities should collaborate with both aviation and non-aviation stakeholders in the development of comprehensive policies, regulations, standards, and procedures for the drone industry. This collaboration should be further strengthened by engaging military aviation personnel with experience in both manned and unmanned aircraft, whose operational expertise can contribute to more robust and informed regulatory frameworks. Additionally, safety investigation reports for drone-related incidents and accidents should consistently include safety recommendations to support the safe and sustainable growth of the drone sector.

9.6 Areas for Future Research

- Future research may explore the development of globally standardised terminology for drone-related concepts to support greater harmonisation in academic, regulatory, and operational contexts. Additionally, research may also examine the use of gender-neutral terminology within the drone industry (European Parliament 2018, United Nations 2020).
- Future research may also explore the standardisation of drone categorisation, which could serve as the foundation for well-structured training programmes and licensing requirements for both drone operators and maintenance personnel.
- Future research may conduct a more detailed evaluation of the adequacy of RASPs and NASPs in addressing drone-related safety risks, taking into account the unique political, economic, social, technological, environmental, and legal contexts of individual regions or States (Washington State University 2025).
- An in-depth study of drone-related safety investigation reports may be conducted to identify the discrepancies, propose improvements for future investigations, and develop generalised guidelines for the drone industry based on the safety recommendations contained within the existing reports.
- Effective strategies for managing inter-drone operations to prevent mid-air collisions between drones could also form part of the future research.
- As previously highlighted in the conclusion of Chapter 2 (Literature Review), cybersecurity challenges in drone operations may be examined in greater depth to propose effective mitigation strategies. Additionally, future studies could explore the practical challenges associated with implementing existing drone regulations, with a view to improving regulatory compliance and operational safety.

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Appendix A
SWOT Analysis and TOWS Matrix

Table 1. SWOT Analysis (Liangrokapart and Sittiwatethanasiri 2023)

Strengths (S)		Weaknesses (W)	
S1	GASP 2023–2025 advises States and industry stakeholders to proactively manage emerging issues through structured mechanisms	W1	GASP 2023–2025 does not explicitly address drones
S2	GASP 2023–2025 encourages the adoption of new technologies, procedures, and operational practices to mitigate the risks associated with the emerging challenges		
Opportunities (O)		Threats (T)	
O1	The current editions of AP-RASP, AFI-RASP, MID-RASP, SAMSP, and the NASPs of Australia, China, Sierra Leone, Iran, UAE, Jamaica, and Finland explicitly identify drones as an emerging risk	T1	Drones have not been addressed in the current editions of the NACC RASP and in the NASPs for Bhutan, Cyprus, Estonia (SPAS), Ethiopia, Guyana, Iceland (IPAS), Indonesia, Italy (SPAS), Kazakhstan (KASP), Lebanon, Maldives, Pakistan, Philippines, Rwanda, and KSA
O2	MID-RASP underscores the role of both manned and unmanned aircraft operators in mitigating drone-related risks	T2	The current editions of SAMSP, India NASP, and UAE NASP show inconsistencies in the use and definition of key terms such as UAS and RPAS
O3	EPAS 2023–2025 emphasises enhanced civil-military cooperation, aiming for drone regulations to benefit from military experience in UAS operations; UK NASP 2022–2024 also identifies military as a key stakeholder		
O4	Australian NASP 2024–2027 highlights the efforts to enhance drone detection around aerodromes		
O5	India NASP 2024–2028 and Sierra Leone NASP 2022–2026 include agriculture, mapping, surveying, mining, and aerial filming as near-term drone application areas		

Table 2. TOWS Matrix (Benzaghta et al. 2021)

External Factors (T, O)	Strengths (S)	Weaknesses (W)
Internal Factors (S, W)		
Opportunities (O)	SO Strategies	WO Strategies
Threats (T)	ST Strategies	WT Strategies

Table 3. SO Strategies

	S1	S2
O1	S1O1	S2O1
O2	S1O2	S2O2
O3	S1O3	S2O3
O4	S1O4	S2O4
O5	S1O5	S2O5

Table 4. ST Strategies

	S1	S2
T1	S1T1	S2T1
T2	S1T2	S2T2

Table 5. WO Strategies

	W1
O1	W1O1
O2	W1O2
O3	W1O3
O4	W1O4
O5	W1O5

Table 6. WT Strategies

	W1
T1	W1T1
T2	W1T2

Table 7. Strategic Options

S/No.	Strategic Options	S/W	O/T	Remarks
1	S1O1	GASP 2023–2025 advises States and industry stakeholders to proactively manage emerging issues through structured mechanisms	The current editions of AP-RASP, AFI-RASP, MID-RASP, SAMSP, and the NASPs of Australia, China, Sierra Leone, Iran, UAE, Jamaica, and Finland explicitly identify drones as an emerging risk	Related (Not Selected–addressed under W1O2 and W1T2)

S/No.	Strategic Options	S/W	O/T	Remarks
2	S1O2	GASP 2023–2025 advises States and industry stakeholders to proactively manage emerging issues through structured mechanisms	MID-RASP underscores the role of both manned and unmanned aircraft operators in mitigating drone-related risks	Not related
3	S1O3	GASP 2023–2025 advises States and industry stakeholders to proactively manage emerging issues through structured mechanisms	EPAS 2023–2025 emphasises enhanced civil-military cooperation, aiming for drone regulations to benefit from military experience in UAS operations; UK NASP 2022–2024 also identifies military as a key stakeholder	Not related
4	S1O4	GASP 2023–2025 advises States and industry stakeholders to proactively manage emerging issues through structured mechanisms	Australian NASP 2024–2027 highlights the efforts to enhance drone detection around aerodromes	Not related
5	S1O5	GASP 2023–2025 advises States and industry stakeholders to proactively manage emerging issues through structured mechanisms	India NASP 2024–2028 and Sierra Leone NASP 2022–2026 include agriculture, mapping, surveying, mining, and aerial filming as near-term drone application areas	Not related
6	S2O1	GASP 2023–2025 encourages the adoption of new technologies, procedures, and operational practices to mitigate the risks associated with the emerging challenges	The current editions of AP-RASP, AFI-RASP, MID-RASP, SAMSP, and the NASPs of Australia, China, Sierra Leone, Iran, UAE, Jamaica, and Finland explicitly identify drones as an emerging risk	Not related
7	S2O2	GASP 2023–2025 encourages the adoption of new technologies, procedures, and operational practices to mitigate the risks associated with the	MID-RASP underscores the role of both manned and unmanned aircraft operators in mitigating drone-related risks	Not related

S/No.	Strategic Options	S/W	O/T	Remarks
		emerging challenges		
8	S2O3	GASP 2023–2025 encourages the adoption of new technologies, procedures, and operational practices to mitigate the risks associated with the emerging challenges	EPAS 2023–2025 emphasises enhanced civil-military cooperation, aiming for drone regulations to benefit from military experience in UAS operations; UK NASP 2022–2024 also identifies military as a key stakeholder	Not related
9	S2O4	GASP 2023–2025 encourages the adoption of new technologies, procedures, and operational practices to mitigate the risks associated with the emerging challenges	Australian NASP 2024–2027 highlights the efforts to enhance drone detection around aerodromes	Not related
10	S2O5	GASP 2023–2025 encourages the adoption of new technologies, procedures, and operational practices to mitigate the risks associated with the emerging challenges	India NASP 2024–2028 and Sierra Leone NASP 2022–2026 include agriculture, mapping, surveying, mining, and aerial filming as near-term drone application areas	Not related
11	S1T1	GASP 2023–2025 advises States and industry stakeholders to proactively manage emerging issues through structured mechanisms	Drones have not been addressed in the current editions of the NACC RASP and in the NASPs for Bhutan, Cyprus, Estonia (SPAS), Ethiopia, Guyana, Iceland (IPAS), Indonesia, Italy (SPAS), Kazakhstan (KASP), Lebanon, Maldives, Pakistan, Philippines, Rwanda, and KSA	Not related
12	S1T2	GASP 2023–2025 advises States and industry stakeholders to proactively manage emerging issues through	The current editions of SAMSP, India NASP, and UAE NASP show inconsistencies in the use and definition of key terms such as	Not related

S/No.	Strategic Options	S/W	O/T	Remarks
		structured mechanisms	UAS and RPAS	
13	S2T1	GASP 2023–2025 encourages the adoption of new technologies, procedures, and operational practices to mitigate the risks associated with the emerging challenges	Drones have not been addressed in the current editions of the NACC RASP and in the NASPs for Bhutan, Cyprus, Estonia (SPAS), Ethiopia, Guyana, Iceland (IPAS), Indonesia, Italy (SPAS), Kazakhstan (KASP), Lebanon, Maldives, Pakistan, Philippines, Rwanda, and KSA	Not related
14	S2T2	GASP 2023–2025 encourages the adoption of new technologies, procedures, and operational practices to mitigate the risks associated with the emerging challenges	The current editions of SAMSP, India NASP, and UAE NASP show inconsistencies in the use and definition of key terms such as UAS and RPAS	Not related
15	W1O1	GASP 2023–2025 does not explicitly address drones	The current editions of AP-RASP, AFI-RASP, MID-RASP, SAMSP, and the NASPs of Australia, China, Sierra Leone, Iran, UAE, Jamaica, and Finland explicitly identify drones as an emerging risk	Related (Not Selected–addressed under W1O2 and W1T2)
16	W1O2	GASP 2023–2025 does not explicitly address drones	MID-RASP underscores the role of both manned and unmanned aircraft operators in mitigating drone-related risks	Related (Selected)
17	W1O3	GASP 2023–2025 does not explicitly address drones	EPAS 2023–2025 emphasises enhanced civil-military cooperation, aiming for drone regulations to benefit from military experience in UAS operations; UK NASP 2022–2024 also identifies military as a key stakeholder	Related (Selected)

S/No.	Strategic Options	S/W	O/T	Remarks
18	W1O4	GASP 2023–2025 does not explicitly address drones	Australian NASP 2024–2027 highlights the efforts to enhance drone detection around aerodromes	Related (Not selected–covered in literature, see Sections 2.4 and 2.6.2)
19	W1O5	GASP 2023–2025 does not explicitly address drones	India NASP 2024–2028 and Sierra Leone NASP 2022–2026 include agriculture, mapping, surveying, mining, and aerial filming as near-term drone application areas	Related (Selected)
20	W1T1	GASP 2023–2025 does not explicitly address drones	Drones have not been addressed in the current editions of the NACC RASP and in the NASPs for Bhutan, Cyprus, Estonia (SPAS), Ethiopia, Guyana, Iceland (IPAS), Indonesia, Italy (SPAS), Kazakhstan (KASP), Lebanon, Maldives, Pakistan, Philippines, Rwanda, and KSA	Related (Not Selected–addressed under W1O2 and W1T2)
21	W1T2	GASP 2023–2025 does not explicitly address drones	The current editions of SAMSP, India NASP, and UAE NASP show inconsistencies in the use and definition of key terms such as UAS and RPAS	Related (Selected)

Table 8. Course of Action

S/No.	Strategic Options	S/W	O/T	Strategy Description
1	W1O2	GASP 2023–2025 does not explicitly address drones	MID-RASP underscores the role of both manned and unmanned aircraft operators in	Utilise the emphasis in MID-RASP on the shared responsibility of manned and unmanned aircraft operators to inform and support the

S/No.	Strategic Options	S/W	O/T	Strategy Description
			mitigating drone-related risks	inclusion of drone-specific risks and mitigation strategies in future updates of GASP
2	W1O3	GASP 2023–2025 does not explicitly address drones	EPAS 2023–2025 emphasises enhanced civil-military cooperation, aiming for drone regulations to benefit from military experience in UAS operations; UK NASP 2022–2024 also identifies military as a key stakeholder	Leverage the emphasis on civil-military cooperation in EPAS and UK NASP to support the inclusion of drone-related safety considerations in future editions of GASP, drawing on military expertise in UAS operations to address the current omission
3	W1O5	GASP 2023–2025 does not explicitly address drones	India NASP 2024–2028 and Sierra Leone NASP 2022–2026 include agriculture, mapping, surveying, mining, and aerial filming as near-term drone application areas	Leverage the recognition of near-term drone applications such as agriculture, mapping, surveying, mining, and aerial filming in the NASPs of India and Sierra Leone to promote the inclusion of drone-specific operational contexts and associated safety considerations in future editions of GASP, thereby addressing its current omission and aligning global strategy with emerging practical use cases
4	W1T2	GASP 2023–2025 does not explicitly address drones	The current editions of SAMSP, India NASP, and UAE NASP show inconsistencies in the use and definition of key terms such as UAS and RPAS	Promote the inclusion of drones in future editions of GASP using standardised terminology to address the current omission and help mitigate inconsistencies in definitions across existing national and regional safety plans